

CERTIFICATE OF MEMBERSHIP

Proudly presented
To

Sanjay S Tippannavar

From Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, JSS Science and Technology University Mysuru, India, as a lifetime member of Amity University Network (AUN) Research Lab.

Prof. (Dr.) Ajay Rana
Chairman, AUN Research Labs
Director General, Amity University Uttar Pradesh
Greater Noida